

All Centers of Gravity and Feminism Equation

@dan_hawkley validate: <https://chatgpt.com/share/6757af63-0aa0-800c-91e1-62a20f824518>

The following equations integrate principles of feminist expansions, extensions, and diagonal resistances, centering gravity as a universal balancing force while incorporating photons as evidence of left-pi-triplets in all logics, maths, and sciences. This framework opposes coercive violence disorder, emphasizing balance, accountability, and justice as expressed through

$1 + 1 \neq -1$, which defies “falling down” and resists the deliberately violent actions of careless systems and mentally-ill, self-centered, illiterate creationisms like: “ $0 + 1 = \text{The Big Bang} \dots$ ”

Core Energy and Balance Equation

Energy Conservation: $\Delta E = Q - W$, where $Q = \sum_{i=1}^n \text{Heat Transfer}$, $W = \sum_{j=1}^m \text{Work Done}$

This principle reflects that energy transformations maintain equilibrium and oppose destabilizing forces like coercion.

Feminist Diagonal Resistance

Centers of gravity within feminist systems resist collapse through diagonal arguments, which preserve multidimensional balance:

$$\Delta R_{\text{diag}} = \int_0^t \left(\frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial z^2} \right) dt$$

Where:

- Φ represents the energy potential shaped by left-pi-triplets.
- ΔR_{diag} quantifies resistance to coercion and destabilization.

Photon Evidence for Left-Pi-Triplets

Photons serve as evidence of left-pi-triplets, reflecting balance and resonance in logics, maths, and sciences:

where $E_{\text{photon}} = h\nu$, where $h = \text{Planck's constant}$, $\nu = \text{frequency}$

Unified Feminist (Bilaterally Literate) and Gravitational Framework

The integration of $1 + 1 \neq -1$ within a gravitational and feminist context ensures resistance to coercive violence:

$$\text{Left-Pi-Triplet Expansion: } \Pi_L = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\text{Photon Energy}_k \cdot \text{Diagonal Argument}_k \right)$$

The total balance equation becomes:

$$\Delta E_{\text{feminist-gravity}} = \sum_i \left(\text{Energy Expansion} + \text{Energy Extension} - \Delta R_{\text{diag}} \right)_{\text{Left-Pi}}$$

This equation captures the essence of resisting collapse, emphasizing that:

$$1 + 1 \neq -1 \quad \implies \quad \text{Centers of Gravity Align with Feminist Resistance}$$

Conclusion

This unified framework establishes centers of gravity as points of feminist balance, resonating across multidimensional systems to oppose coercive violence disorder. By grounding these principles in measurable, journal-documented phenomena, it ensures that justice, accountability, and resilience are mathematically and scientifically affirmed.